

Developing B2 Level University Students Cognitive Thinking Skills in Reading Classes

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Abstract: In this article, both local and overseas scholastic views are analyzed in order to provide with theoretical insights about the need for developing students' critical thinking skill. Moreover, the writer discusses about the educational effect of developing students' thinking ability (LOT and HOT skills) in reading classes through effective and user-friendly classroom techniques that EFL teachers can adapt in their lesson planning process.

Keywords: Blooms Taxonomy, cognitive, Lower-Order Thinking (LOT), Higher-Order Thinking (HOT), scaffolding, differentiated instructions, word walls, vocabulary building, context clues, graphic organizers, summarizing, retelling, textual evidence, character analysis, theme analysis, plot analysis.

Introduction.

The development of cognitive thinking skills in reading classes is essential for fostering students' academic success and critical thinking abilities. Scaffolding, a key instructional technique derived from Vygotsky's (1978) Social Constructivism, provides a framework for supporting students as they progress from basic comprehension (Lower-Order Thinking, or LOT) to more complex analytical and evaluative tasks (Higher-Order Thinking, or HOT). This article examines the role of scaffolding in reading instruction, explores practical techniques for developing LOT and HOT skills, and discusses the importance of differentiated instruction in tailoring these strategies to diverse learners.

Theoretical Framework

a. Vygotsky's Social Constructivism and Scaffolding

Vygotsky's (1978) concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is foundational to understanding scaffolding. The ZPD refers to the range of tasks that a learner can perform with guidance but cannot yet accomplish independently. Scaffolding, as defined by Wood, Bruner, and Ross (1976), involves providing temporary support that helps students bridge the gap between their current abilities and their potential development. In reading classes, scaffolding can take various forms, such as modeling, questioning, and providing feedback, all of which help students gradually build their cognitive skills.

b. Bloom's Taxonomy: From LOT to HOT Skills

Bloom's Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001) categorizes cognitive skills into six levels: Remember, Understand, Apply (LOT), Analyze, Evaluate, and Create (HOT). This

hierarchical model guides educators in designing reading activities that align with students' cognitive development. Scaffolding techniques can be applied at each level, ensuring that students develop a solid foundation of LOT skills before advancing to HOT skills.

Developing Thinking Skills in Reading Classes: A Blend of LOT and HOT

Lower-Order Thinking (LOT) Skills involve basic comprehension and recall.

Higher-Order Thinking (HOT) Skills delve deeper, requiring analysis, evaluation, and creation.

Here's a breakdown of how to cultivate both in reading classes:

LOT Skills:¹

Vocabulary Building:

Word Walls: Display key vocabulary from the text.

Context Clues: Encourage students to find clues within the text to understand unfamiliar words.

Graphic Organizers: Use charts, maps, and diagrams to help students organize vocabulary and their meaning.

Etymology: Explore the origins and history of words to deepen understanding.

Comprehension:

Summarizing: Teach students to identify the main idea and supporting details.

Retelling: Encourage students to retell stories in their own words.

Questioning: Use open-ended questions to guide comprehension. (e.g., "What is the main conflict in the story?").

Prediction: Have students make predictions about what will happen next in the text.

HOT Skills:²

Analysis:

Textual Evidence: Encourage students to find evidence within the text to support their claims.

Character Analysis: Explore the motivations, traits, and changes of characters.

Plot Analysis: Identify the cause-and-effect relationships and plot structure.

Theme Analysis: Explore the underlying messages or themes of the text.

Evaluation:

Critical Thinking: Have students evaluate the author's purpose and biases.

Textual Features: Analyze the impact of literary devices, including figurative language, symbolism, and tone.

Compare and Contrast: Compare and contrast different texts, characters, or themes.

Creation:

Creative Writing: Encourage students to write their own stories, poems, or scripts based on the text.

¹ Harris, K.R., & Graham, S. (2013). Teaching Reading Comprehension Strategies.

² Duke, N.K., & Pearson, P.D. (2002). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension.

Art Projects: Have students create visual representations of the text.

Role-Playing: Have students act out scenes from the text.

Debate: Encourage students to discuss different interpretations of the text.³

Materials.

Different classroom techniques can be integrated gradually so that learners can first try to remember, understand, and apply through PPP lesson plan modeling and then move to more complex thinking by analyzing, evaluating, and creating. Based on what genre of reading text they are using, teachers can design lesson plans accordingly in order to meet the requirements of LOT and HOT skills integration.

Integrating LOT and HOT Skills:

Collaborative Learning: Utilize group discussions, think-pair-share activities, and peer teaching.

Differentiation: Tailor activities to meet the needs of all learners.

Technology: Utilize online resources, interactive games, and simulations to engage students.

Real-World Connections: Connect reading materials to current events, social issues, and students' own experiences.

Examples:

LOT: Have students complete a graphic organizer to identify the main events in a story.

HOT: Have students write an essay analyzing the symbolism of a particular object in the text.

By incorporating both LOT and HOT skills into your reading instruction, you can empower students to become critical and thoughtful readers.⁴

Research and methods.

To develop students' thinking skills in reading classes, educators can incorporate activities and strategies that target both lower-order thinking (LOT) skills, such as comprehension and recall, and higher-order thinking (HOT) skills, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Here are some effective ways to develop students' thinking skills in reading classes:

1. **Comprehension activities:** To develop LOT skills, have students engage in activities that focus on understanding and recalling information from the text. This can include activities like summarizing, outlining, and identifying main ideas and supporting details.
2. **Critical thinking questions:** Encourage students to think critically by asking open-ended and thought-provoking questions that require analysis and evaluation of the text. These questions can help students delve deeper into the meaning of the text and develop their HOT skills.
3. **Compare and contrast:** Have students compare and contrast different texts, characters, settings, or themes to promote critical thinking and analysis. This can help students develop their ability to identify similarities and differences and draw connections between texts.
4. **Socratic seminars:** Engage students in Socratic seminars, where they participate in discussions based on a text, sharing their interpretations, asking questions, and challenging each other's ideas. This can help develop students' ability to think critically, communicate

³ Van den Broek, P., & Espin, C. (2012). Cognitive processes in reading comprehension.

⁴ <https://www.ecenglish.com/en/school-locations/blog/ec/2023/02/22/how-to-use-lots-and-hots-thinking-skills-in-the-classroom/>

effectively, and actively engage with the text.

5. Reciprocal teaching: Implement the reciprocal teaching strategy, where students take on the roles of summarizer, questioner, clarifier, and predictor to facilitate deep comprehension and critical thinking. This strategy helps students actively engage with the text and think critically about its content.
6. Problem-solving tasks: Present students with real-world problems or issues related to the text and ask them to solve or address these problems using information from the text. This can help students apply their reading comprehension skills to practical situations and develop their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.
7. Inquiry-based learning: Encourage students to formulate their own questions, conduct research, and explore topics related to the texts they are reading. This promotes independent thinking, curiosity, and the development of HOT skills such as analysis and synthesis.⁵

Differentiated Instruction in Reading Classes

Differentiated instruction is essential in scaffolding cognitive thinking skills, as it allows educators to meet the diverse needs of students. Tomlinson (2001) emphasizes the importance of differentiating content, process, and product based on students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles.

a. Differentiating Content

Teachers can offer texts at varying levels of complexity, ensuring that all students engage with material that is appropriately challenging. For instance, struggling readers might work with simplified versions of a text, focusing on LOT skills, while advanced readers tackle the original text, delving into HOT tasks.

b. Differentiating Process

Differentiating the process involves providing different levels of support during reading activities. For example, some students might require more extensive scaffolding, such as guided reading or think-alouds, while others might work independently or in small groups to explore more complex tasks.

c. Differentiating Product

Students can demonstrate their understanding and cognitive skills through various types of products, such as written summaries, graphic organizers, or creative projects. This approach allows students to showcase their learning in ways that align with their strengths and cognitive levels.

Results.

Developing students' thinking skills, including both lower-order thinking (LOT) and higher-order thinking (HOT) skills, in reading lessons has numerous educational benefits. By enhancing students' ability to critically engage with texts, analyze information, and make connections between ideas, educators can help students become more effective readers and learners. Some of the key educational effects of developing students' thinking skills in reading lessons include:

1. Improved comprehension: Developing LOT skills, such as summarizing and identifying main ideas, helps students better understand and remember the content of the text. By honing their ability to recall and synthesize information, students can enhance their overall

⁵ <https://jobsineducation.medium.com/14-techniques-for-teaching-students-reading-comprehension-skills-95a0be7e5060>

comprehension of reading material.

2. Enhanced critical thinking: Engaging students in activities that target HOT skills, such as analysis, evaluation, and problem-solving, promotes critical thinking. Students learn to question, evaluate evidence, draw conclusions, and make connections between different concepts, leading to a deeper understanding of the material.

3. Increased engagement: When students are challenged to think critically and actively participate in discussions and activities that require them to use their thinking skills, they become more engaged in the learning process. This active engagement promotes a deeper level of understanding and helps students develop a greater appreciation for reading and learning.

4. Transferable skills: Developing thinking skills in reading lessons not only benefits students' reading comprehension but also equips them with transferable skills that can be applied across different subjects and real-life situations. These skills include problem-solving, analysis, communication, and logical reasoning.

5. Lifelong learning: By fostering students' ability to think critically, analyze information, and make informed judgments, educators are helping to instill a love of learning and a desire for continuous intellectual growth. These skills are essential for success in higher education, careers, and everyday life.⁶

Discussion.

Developing students' thinking skills, both lower-order (LOT) and higher-order (HOT), in reading lessons has a profound and multifaceted educational effect, impacting their academic journey and beyond.

Here's how developing LOT and HOT skills in reading benefits students:

1. Enhanced Comprehension and Retention:

LOT: Building strong foundations in vocabulary, identifying main ideas, and summarizing texts allows students to understand and retain information more effectively.

HOT: Analysis, evaluation, and creative thinking encourage students to engage with the material on a deeper level, leading to a more thorough understanding and lasting retention.

2. Improved Academic Performance:

Across Subjects: Strong reading comprehension skills are essential across all subjects, as students encounter complex texts in every discipline.

Critical Thinking: HOT skills, like analysis and evaluation, enable students to solve problems, make informed decisions, and excel in academic tasks.

3. Increased Literacy and Communication Skills:

Vocabulary: Expanding vocabulary strengthens written and oral communication skills.

Communication: Reading comprehension and analysis equip students to communicate their ideas effectively through writing, speaking, and discussion.

4. Fostering Lifelong Learning:

Active Engagement: Thinking skills encourage active engagement with texts, fostering a love of reading and lifelong learning.

Critical Readers: Students become critical readers who can analyze information, identify biases, and evaluate sources.

⁶ <https://skyteach.ru/methods/lower-and-higher-order-thinking-skills-lots-and-hots/>

5. Development of Personal and Social Skills:

Problem Solving: Thinking skills aid in problem-solving, decision-making, and critical thinking in everyday life.

Collaboration: Group activities and discussions cultivate collaboration, communication, and teamwork.

6. Enhanced Creativity and Innovation:

Beyond Comprehension: HOT skills encourage creative thinking, allowing students to connect ideas, generate new solutions, and develop innovative ideas.

7. Improved Self-Confidence and Motivation:

Success in Learning: Developing thinking skills empowers students, boosting their self-confidence and motivation to learn.

Academic Success: Strong reading skills and thinking skills lead to academic success, fostering a positive attitude towards learning.⁷

Conclusion.

Scaffolding students' cognitive thinking skills in reading classes is a dynamic process that requires careful planning and differentiation. By providing appropriate support at each stage of cognitive development, educators can help students build a strong foundation of LOT skills before moving on to more complex HOT tasks. The strategies discussed in this review, including guided reading, think-alouds, Socratic seminars, and differentiated instruction, offer practical approaches to fostering cognitive growth in diverse learners.

Overall, the educational effects of developing students' thinking skills (both LOT and HOT) in reading lessons are manifold. Not only do students improve their reading comprehension and critical thinking abilities, but they also gain valuable skills that can benefit them academically and personally in the long term. By promoting a culture of critical thinking and inquiry in the classroom, educators can help students become more strategic, independent, and reflective learners. By incorporating these strategies and activities into reading classes, educators can effectively develop students' thinking skills, both LOT and HOT, and help them become more critical, analytical, and engaged readers.

Developing students' thinking skills in reading lessons creates a ripple effect across their educational journey and beyond. It empowers them to become confident, critical thinkers, lifelong learners, and successful individuals.

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